

Timeline of the Tetragrammaton renderings in Greek

Pavlos D. Vasileiadis

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

November 17, 2020

Based on “Appendix A” of:

Pavlos D. Vasileiadis, “Aspects of rendering the sacred Tetragrammaton in Greek,”

Open Theology, vol. 1 (2014), pp. 56–88

(online here: <https://zenodo.org/record/4262263>).

The original source and image enriched version of this timeline is available on-line here:

<https://www.timetoast.com/timelines/2423659>

